

ORIGINAL RESEARCH

Impact of E-Commerce Service Quality on Customer Loyalty: A Case of Vietnam

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Abstract

The study measures service quality and customer loyalty among logistics service providers, with customer satisfaction mediating these variables. The survey questionnaire was used to collect 401 data from consumers in Vietnam. Data were analyzed using least-squares analysis (PLS-SEM). The results show that service quality variables such as customer service; product quality; information quality; delivery service; perceived price, and reverse logistics positively influence customer loyalty through customer satisfaction. The results show that customer satisfaction has a direct relationship with customer loyalty. The study recommends that service providers need to upgrade and improve the quality of their services.

Keyword: E-commerce, Service Quality; Customer Loyalty; Vietnam

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1. Introduction

In recent years, "e-commerce" is no longer a strange concept in society or a new field in our country. In the era of digital technology 4.0 and the rapid development of the Internet, the trend of online business or online sales has brought economic efficiency to many business lines in Vietnam.

The e-commerce market is increasingly expanding with many models and participants, and supply chains are also gradually changing towards a more modern direction with the support of digitalization and information technology. Especially in the context of the COVID-19 epidemic, the e-commerce market is becoming more vibrant. Applying digital technology and building new distribution channels is becoming an effective solution for businesses. Viet Nam overcame difficulties and brought new opportunities from the market demand based on changing consumers' buying habits, switching from traditional buying habits to buying goods through e-commerce.

With the strength of a young population and a large proportion of smartphone users, many people transact e-commerce on smartphones. The e-commerce market in Vietnam is currently growing quite rapidly with 35.4

million users and creating generated more than \$2.7 billion in revenue in 2019. The 2019 Southeast Asian e-commerce report by Google, Temasek, and Brain&Company predict the average growth rate for 2015-2025 of Vietnam's e-commerce is 29%. In 2020, the COVID-19 pandemic brought many changes to the economy. The explosive growth of e-commerce has made Vietnam one of the most potential markets in the ASEAN region. It is forecasted that by 2025, Vietnam's e-commerce scale will reach 43 billion USD and rank third in ASEAN.

Wicks and Roethlein (2009) have shown that an organization that consistently satisfies its customers will maintain higher gains and greater profits through increased customer loyalty. Accordingly, most businesses have always strived to win customers' hearts by providing customers with the best benefits so that they become loyal customers to the business's brand. Customers form their preferences regarding perceptions and attitudes about competing brands in their minds, so when customers have a good perception of a brand, they will always choose that brand as a priority in their purchasing decisions. Businesses must find ways to meet customer satisfaction comprehensively by understanding and capturing customer needs;